

Original Research

The Impact of CSR Disclosure on Firm Value in Mining Companies: The Moderating Role of Media Exposure

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of CSR disclosure on firm value, with media exposure as a moderating variable. This research is causal associative study with a quantitative approach. The study employs purposive sampling to determine the sample, resulting in 112 out of a total population of 324 mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period 2020 to 2023. Moderated regression analysis is used in this study. The results show that CSR disclosure has a positive and significant effect on firm value. Media exposure positively and significantly moderates this relationship. Practically, these findings can serve as a consideration for companies in disclosing CSR activities and as input for investors in making investment decision. The implication of this research is to serve as a reference and consideration of the importance of allocating CSR effectively, as it has a positive impact on the development of investment value.

Keywords: CSR, Firm Value, Media Exposure.

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Introduction

The issue of disclosing social responsibility or CSR remains a hot topic among the public due to the level of societal modernization and the negative impacts of corporate activities that can cause environmental damage (Budiarti & Raharjo, 2014). Companies should not solely prioritize the needs of investors and creditors merely to earn profits; they must also consider social and environmental responsibilities. One prominent case in Indonesia regarding corporate social responsibility disclosure that has become a hot issue is the tin mining corruption case, where environmental losses reached 271 trillion (Uniarnews, 2024). This case illustrates the critical importance of monitoring corporate activities and demanding transparency in the management and use of existing resources.

Corporate accountability towards social and environmental aspects is demonstrated through the disclosure of corporate social responsibility (CSR). This has become an important topic in academic literature and business practice. According to the 2020 Minister of Social Affairs regulation on business social and environmental responsibility, it states the "company's commitment to participate in sustainable social development for improving quality of life and the environment." A company's value is not only assessed by its profits but also by the impact its activities have on the community—whether they provide benefits or cause harm. CSR disclosure is a way for companies to showcase their social activities to the public and maintain legitimacy in the eyes of stakeholders. The enhancement of corporate value will be further strengthened if CSR disclosures are publicly communicated by companies through media exposure.

The value of mining companies is not assessed solely based on profit but also on the impact felt by the community from the company's activities—whether those activities provide benefits or, instead, cause harm. This is related to legitimacy theory, which emphasizes the alignment between a company's social behavior and societal expectations, which can influence the company's image. This indicates that poor social and environmental performance can create doubt among investors, potentially leading to a decline in stock prices and firm value (Riswari & Cahyonowati, 2012). Therefore, CSR disclosure allows mining companies to showcase their social activities to the public and maintain legitimacy in the eyes of stakeholders.

The enhancement of firm value will be further strengthened if corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure is made public by mining companies through media exposure. CSR disclosure through media can enhance a company's reputation in the eyes of the public (shareholders). It can be used as part of the organizational development process, the establishment of accepted norms, and the legitimization of CSR practices (Abdullah, 2017). The company website serves as a medium for disclosing CSR fund reports. CSR fund management reports published through the website can be accessed by the public, ensuring transparency and minimizing the risk of fictitious CSR fund reporting.

Research by Karundeng (2017) and Arifin (2022) found that CSR does not have a significant effect on corporate value in the mining sector. This contrasts with studies by Sari (2021), Ariani (2024), Octoriawan & Rusliati (2019) dan Octoriawan & Rusliati (2019), which affirm that CSR disclosure positively influences corporate value. Titi

(2011) emphasizes that CSR disclosure and corporate governance practices together can affect corporate value. Positive signals to investors have the potential to optimize corporate value. This is supported by research from Murnita & Putra (2018), who suggest that profitability and leverage can moderate the relationship between CSR and corporate value. In a broader context, research by Widianingsih (2018) indicates that managerial ownership and audit committees positively influence corporate value, with CSR disclosure acting as a moderating variable. This signifies that CSR disclosure does not stand alone but interacts with other factors in determining corporate value.

Based on the phenomenon of social environmental damage experienced by communities caused by corporate activities that have long-term effects and affect the company's value and image in the public eye, as well as inconsistencies in previous studies by Ghaesani (2017), Panggabean (2018), Bahriansyah & Lestari Ginting (2022) and Anisah (2024), researchers are motivated to conduct research related to corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure and its impact on corporate value. CSR disclosure has a significant effect on corporate value, especially in the context of mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI). Media exposure functions as a moderator that can strengthen this relationship by providing a platform for companies to demonstrate their commitment to social and environmental responsibility.

Research Questions

This study aims to address the following research questions:

1. Does corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR) have an effect on firm value?
2. Does media exposure moderate the relationship between corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR) and firm value?

Literature Review

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory is a management approach that emphasizes the importance of considering the interests of all parties (stakeholders) related to an organization or company, not just shareholders. This theory was deeply developed by Kivits & Sawang (2021). Theory states that all stakeholders in the company have the right to access information related to the company's activities that may influence the decisions being made. Stakeholders are considered important because they have the ability to influence or be influenced by the company's decisions and policies (Wulandari & Wiksuna, 2017).

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory posits that organizations or companies strive to obtain, strengthen, and improve their legitimacy in the eyes of society (Omar, 2017). In this context, legitimacy means that the company's actions and operations must be perceived as aligned with the norms, values, and expectations of the surrounding community. This theory is

widely used in the context of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and social accountability.

Signaling Theory

Signaling theory suggests that the information provider (owner) sends signals in the form of information representing the company's condition, which benefits the information recipients (Lo, 2012). These signals reflect management's evaluation of the company's future prospects and influence potential investors' responses to the company. Such signals also demonstrate management's efforts to realize the owners' intentions (Wongso, 2012). This information serves as an important indicator for investors and business actors in making investment decisions.

Firm Value

Firm Value is measured based on market value, as it reflects the maximum welfare for shareholders when the company's stock price rises. When a company's stock price increases, its corporate value tends to increase as well, and vice (Octoriawan & Rusliati, 2019). According to Sartono (2012), corporate value can be understood as the goal of enhancing shareholders' welfare by optimizing the present value of all profits received by shareholders. Shareholder value increases if the stock price rises. This increase in corporate value positively impacts shareholder value if accompanied by a high return on investment.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), according to the European Commission as cited by Mardikanto, (2014), refers to a concept in which a company voluntarily incorporates social and environmental responsibility into its operational activities and relationships with various stakeholders. This reflects an awareness that responsible practices can lead to sustainable business success. Budimanta, (2008) describes CSR as a company's commitment to improving the quality of life of its stakeholders, including the local community and surrounding social environment, carried out integrally with its sustainable business activities.

Media Exposure

The media plays an important role in driving social mobilization, such as groups concerned with the environment. According to Reverte (2008), the media acts as a source of information about the environment. Media exposure relates to the level of exposure an individual, product, company, or organization has across various media platforms. Companies use media to undertake activities that contribute to increasing firm value, for example through the disclosure of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). The motivations for companies to disclose CSR include enhancing competitiveness, meeting loan contract requirements, satisfying public expectations, legitimizing corporate actions, and attracting investor interest (Sayekti & Wondabio, 2007).

Research findings on the effect of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) on firm value show varying results. Studies by Karundeng (2017) and Arifin (2022) revealed that in the mining sector, CSR does not have a significant effect on firm value. This contrasts

with the findings of Sari (2021), Ariani (2024) and Octoriawan & Rusliati (2019), which show that CSR disclosure positively impacts the enhancement of firm value.

These differences indicate that the effect of CSR is contextual, depending on the industry sector and the internal conditions of the company. Titi (2011) emphasizes the importance of synergy between CSR disclosure and corporate governance (GCG) practices in influencing firm value, as the combination of both can send positive signals to investors. This is supported by Murnita & Putra (2018), who found that profitability and leverage act as moderating variables in the relationship between CSR and firm value.

Therefore, it can be concluded that CSR disclosure does not have a linear or singular impact on firm value, but is influenced and strengthened by various internal company factors such as governance, profitability, ownership structure, and industry characteristics.

Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis

The grand theory applied is the stakeholder theory, which is defined as individuals or groups who have the ability to influence or be influenced by decisions (Rawi & Muchlish, 2010). Stakeholder theory explains the importance of providing information to stakeholders regarding a company's social and environmental responsibilities in order to influence decision-making.

Related to stakeholder theory, companies must enhance their responsibility toward stakeholders. This influences positive responses reflected in increased stock prices, which in turn affect the company's value. Therefore, stakeholder theory emphasizes that companies cannot be separated from their social environment to build trust among stakeholders.

Signaling theory states that the information bearer (the owner of the information) sends signals in the form of data that describe the company's condition, which benefits the receiver. These signals reflect management's assessment of the company's future growth prospects and also influence potential investors' responses toward the company.

Another theory applied is legitimacy theory. This theory explains that a company's legitimacy changes in line with the dynamics of the environment and society in which the company operates (Dowling & Pfeffer, 1975). According to Ghazali & Chariri (2007), legitimacy theory is based on a social contract between the company and society, often represented by the government. Compliance by the company with regulations established by the government is seen as a reflection of society's will. Nurhayati (2011) explains that legitimacy theory emphasizes the alignment of a company's social behavior with societal expectations, which can influence the company's image. When a mismatch occurs between the desires of society and company behavior, legitimacy issues arise. Therefore, CSR disclosure becomes a way for companies to showcase their social activities to the public and maintain legitimacy in the eyes of stakeholders. Efforts to increase corporate social responsibility also have significant benefits such as enhancing the company's reputation and strengthening business strategies.

The conceptual framework of this research serves as a guide as well as a thinking framework and foundation for formulating the research hypotheses to be presented below:

Figure 1. Research Model

Based on stakeholder theory, corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure influences firm value as companies tend to respond to the interests of diverse stakeholders such as employees, consumers, and the wider community (Budianto & Suyono, 2020). Meanwhile, legitimacy theory indicates that CSR can also affect firm value because companies strive to maintain legitimacy and support from society and other stakeholders (Tino & Sudana, 2025). Research by Khofifah (2024) and Abdullah, (2017) found that CSR has a positive and significant effect on firm value. From the above explanation, it can be concluded that CSR positively influences the disclosure of firm value. Therefore, companies can optimize firm value by increasing their disclosure of corporate social responsibility. Based on this review, the first hypothesis of this study is:

H₁: Corporate Social Responsibility has a positive effect on firm value.

According to stakeholder theory, the role of media exposure in influencing CSR's impact on firm value is important because of stakeholder involvement in the business decision-making process. Corporate media exposure, reflected in transparent disclosures through media regarding company report information, indicates the company's ability to meet the needs and expectations of various stakeholders (Julekhah & Rahmawati, 2019). Strong media exposure can strengthen public confidence that the company acts transparently and has a positive impact on the environment and society. Therefore, media exposure plays a crucial role in explaining the relationship between CSR and firm value

from both stakeholder and legitimacy theory perspectives. Research by Prasetyo Agesta (2019) and Anisah (2024) on media exposure and its relation to firm value found that corporate social responsibility disclosure and profitability moderated by media disclosure simultaneously affect firm value. Based on the above review, the second hypothesis of this study is:

H₂: Media exposure strengthens the relationship between corporate social responsibility disclosure and firm value.

Material and Methodology

This study uses a causal associative approach with a quantitative method. The main focus of causal associative research is to explore the relationship between two or more variables related to the research object with a cause-and-effect nature. Research data were obtained from the official IDX website www.idx.go.id and the websites of companies sampled in the research. The sampling technique used is the purposive sampling method with the following criteria:

- I. Mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the period 2020–2023.
- II. Companies that were consecutively listed on the IDX from 2020 to 2023.
- III. Companies that did not generate profit consecutively during the 2020–2023 period.

The sample consisted of 112 companies from a total population of 324 companies over a period of 4 years (2020 to 2023), using secondary data derived from literature reviews of financial reports, annual reports, sustainability reports, and observations of online media through Google News as well as the Indonesia Stock Exchange website.

Operational Definition of Variables

The variables in this study are described operationally as concrete steps measured using instruments or measurement methods.

In this study, the dependent variable is firm value, and CSR is the independent variable. Media exposure is the moderating variable that influences (strengthens or weakens) the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The control variables in this study are profitability and firm size.

Table 1. Measurement of Variables

Variable Name	Symbol	Calculation Method	Source
Corporate Social Responsibility	CSRI _j	1: discloses according to the index, 0: does not disclose according to the index	(Chung & Pruitt, 2015)
Firm Value	FV	<i>Tobin's Q</i>	(Ningrum, 2022 : 20-21)
<i>Media exposure</i>	ME	1: companies that disclose CSR activities on their website, social media such as online news, company Instagram, and so on; 0: companies that do not disclose CSR activities on their website, social media such as online news, company Instagram	(Ghita, 2019)
Company Size	FS	(Ln) total assets of the company	(Madan & Wang, 2024: 48-49)
Profitability	PRO	ROA	(Fitriana, 2024: 46-47)

Data Analysis

The analysis methods used include multiple linear regression analysis and Moderate Regression Analysis (MRA), a stepwise regression method (hierarchical regression analysis). This approach is used because this study involves moderating variables (Apriyani, 2019), employing Eviews 13 software. This analysis method is used to analyze the effect of CSR on firm value as well as its interaction with media exposure. The models formed are as follows:

$$FV = \alpha + \beta_1CSRI_j + \beta_2FS + \beta_3PRO + e \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$FV = \alpha + \beta_1CSRI_j + \beta_2ME + \beta_3FS + \beta_4PRO + e \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$FV = \alpha + \beta_1CSRI_j + \beta_2ME + \beta_3CSRI_j * ME + \beta_4FS + \beta_5PRO + e \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Description:

FV = *Firm Value*

CSRI_j = *Corporate Social Responsibility Indeks*

ME = *Media exposure*

FS = *Firm Size*

PRO = *Profitability*

$\alpha = \text{Constant}$

$\beta = \text{Regression Coefficient}$

$e = \text{Error term}$

Model FV (1) represents the direct relationship between the Corporate Social Responsibility Index (CSRI) and firm value (FV), while controlling for firm size (FS) and profitability (PRO). This model aims to identify the influence of CSR on firm value without considering moderation factors.

In Model FV (2), media exposure (ME) is added as an independent variable. This model explores the influence of media exposure on firm value alongside CSR, firm size, and profitability. It enables researchers to understand how media exposure may directly affect firm value.

Model FV (3) is an interaction model that includes the interaction term between CSR and media exposure. By adding the product of CSRI and ME, this model aims to assess whether media exposure moderates the relationship between CSR and firm value. This is the most complex model, providing insights into how the effect of CSR on firm value may vary depending on the level of media exposure.

Results

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics describe data based on mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values. Based on the descriptive statistics test results in Table 2, the data count (n) used in this study is 112, which can be detailed as follows.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistic

a	FV	CSR	ME	FS	PRO
Mean	1.947210	35.90179	2.750000	28.99601	0.131465
Median	1.097810	34.00000	3.000000	28.90551	0.081406
Maximum	18.10736	88.00000	3.000000	32.74226	0.617597
Minimum	0.182664	2.000000	0.000000	23.66444	0.002392
Std. Dev.	2.999124	18.27121	0.741316	1.827575	0.139084
Skewness	3.613400	0.247770	-2.765563	-0.587218	1.790390
Kurtosis	15.89071	2.511435	9.155872	3.429805	5.689077
Jarque-Bera	1019.186	2.259856	319.6112	7.298808	93.58122
Probability	0.000000	0.323056	0.000000	0.026007	0.000000
Sum	218.0875	4021.000	308.0000	3247.553	14.72404
Sum Sq. Dev.	998.4164	37055.92	61.00000	370.7433	2.147211
Observations	112	112	112	112	112

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics results, where the mean is used to understand the average data values within the sample. The standard deviation serves to measure the degree of data variation; if the standard deviation is larger than the mean for a certain variable, it indicates that the variable's data has a wide spread and considerable fluctuation, and vice versa. Additionally, the minimum and maximum values illustrate which samples have the lowest and highest values over the three consecutive years of the study period.

Classical Assumption Tests

From the model testing results above, the Chow test and Lagrange Multiplier test indicate that the most suitable model is the common effect model, while the Hausman test suggests the random effect model. Based on these results, the decision was made to use the common effect model as the basis for further analysis. Therefore, classical assumptions will be tested on this common effect model, and the analysis results will be interpreted using the common effect approach to ensure the accuracy and validity of the model used in the study.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is necessary to analyze the presence of differences in the variance of residuals from one observation period to another (Sujarweni, V, 2019)

Tabel 3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.471222	1.984082	1.245524	0.2158
CSR	0.004863	0.006884	0.706367	0.4816
ME	-0.052736	0.239620	-0.220081	0.8262
FS	-0.112296	0.066631	-1.685336	0.0950
PRO	0.556879	0.849928	0.655207	0.5138
R-squared	0.029177	Mean dependent var		-0.695354
Adjusted R-squared	-0.008525	S.D. dependent var		1.137507
S.E. of regression	1.142345	Akaike info criterion		3.149233
Sum squared resid	134.4100	Schwarz criterion		3.273406
Log likelihood	-165.0586	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.199581
F-statistic	0.773890	Durbin-Watson stat		1.241593
Prob(F-statistic)	0.544635			

To interpret the results of the heteroscedasticity test using the Glejser test, one only needs to look at the 'Prob.' value in the output table, where the variable RESABS serves as the dependent variable. From the output, it can be observed that the significance value (Prob.) for all independent variables is greater than 0.05. Therefore, based on the decision criteria for the Glejser test, it can be concluded that this regression model does not have a heteroscedasticity problem.

Multikolinieritas Test

The multicollinearity test, as explained by Ghozali (2018: 105), is an important regression model test to examine whether there is correlation among the independent variables, because the absence of correlation among independent variables is an indication that the regression model is good.

Table 4. Multikolinieritas Test

	CSR	FV	FS	ME	PRO
CSR	1.000000	0.179965	0.268634	-0.431501	-0.003717
FV	0.179965	1.000000	0.331774	0.268030	0.745048
FS	0.268634	0.331774	1.000000	-0.022278	0.325120
ME	-0.431501	0.268030	-0.022278	1.000000	0.216263
PRO	-0.003717	0.745048	0.325120	0.216263	1.000000

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test above, it is understood that no independent variable has a correlation value exceeding 0.90 (Ghozali 2018: 83), therefore it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity among the independent variables in the regression.

Determination Coefficient Test

The determination coefficient test is conducted to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The results of the determination test are as follows:

Table 5. Determination Coefficient Test

R-squared	0.634814
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Based on the common effect model output, the coefficient of determination (R^2) value is recorded at 0.634814, which is the square of the correlation coefficient (R), namely 0.7967522. This R^2 value of 0.634814 or 63.4814% indicates that the variables of CSR, media exposure, along with control variables such as firm size and profitability, together explain 63.4814% of the variation in firm value. Meanwhile, the remaining 36.5186% (100% minus 63.4814%) is influenced by other variables not included in this regression model, often referred to as error (ϵ), which can be calculated using the formula $\epsilon = 1 - R^2$.

Partial Test (t-Statistic)

The t-test is used to describe the partial effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The results of the t-statistic test are as follows:

Table 6 Parsial Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.234943	1.899351	-0.123696	0.9018
CSR	0.026297	0.006590	3.990137	0.0001
ME	0.811330	0.229387	3.536952	0.0006
FS	0.040818	0.063786	0.639933	0.5236
PRO	8.542705	0.813632	10.49947	0.0000

The t-statistic test is fundamentally conducted to measure the extent of the influence of each independent variable individually on the dependent variable. In this context, the hypothesis test is used to determine the effect of each independent variable, namely CSR, media exposure, and control variables including firm size and profitability, on the dependent variable, which is firm value.

The t-statistic test on CSR's effect on firm value shows that CSR has a positive and significant influence on the firm value of the companies studied. This is based on the probability value of 0.0001, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. The regression coefficient of CSR is positive, at 0.026297, indicating a positive relationship between CSR and firm value. Therefore, it can be said that the first hypothesis, which states that CSR positively and significantly influences firm value in mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2020-2023, is accepted.

In the moderation test, the effect of CSR on firm value is not significant ($0.4979 > 0.05$), and the effect of media exposure on firm value is also not significant ($0.7492 > 0.05$). However, the interaction effect between CSR and media exposure (CSRME) is significant ($0.0125 < 0.05$), indicating that media exposure acts as a moderator of the influence of CSR on firm value. Thus, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis, which states that media exposure strengthens the relationship between CSR and firm value in the companies studied, is accepted.

Discussion

The results indicate that CSR has a positive and significant effect on firm value. This finding aligns with stakeholder theory, which emphasizes the importance of the relationship between the company and stakeholders such as employees, consumers, investors, local communities, and government. Within this theoretical framework, companies that actively disclose and implement social responsibility gain trust and strong support from stakeholders. This trust is then reflected in the market's perception of the company's reputation, which helps to optimize firm value among stakeholders.

This study also reinforces previous research, including studies by Praditya & Utomo (2022) and (Hermawan, 2021), which found that the level of CSR disclosure is positively correlated with an increase in firm value, as indicated by metrics such as price-to-book value (PBV) or Tobin's Q. This shows that the market values companies that are active in non-financial reporting and are committed to sustainability principles.

For corporate management, these findings provide a strong rationale to promote CSR as part of a long-term corporate strategy. Developing sustainable CSR programs that are integrated with core business strategies not only strengthens the company's position in facing social and regulatory pressures but also provides long-term competitive advantages. Furthermore, companies need to improve the quality of CSR reporting by adhering to international standards such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) to enhance stakeholder trust in the integrity of the reports presented.

The research findings explain that media exposure acts as a moderating variable to enhance the relationship between CSR and firm value. This finding provides important insights into understanding the mechanism by which CSR can have a more effective impact on firm value when supported by adequate media exposure.

From the stakeholder theory perspective, these results confirm that media exposure plays a strategic role in conveying CSR information to various stakeholder groups. Media functions as the primary channel for communicating a company's social and environmental activities, including policies, programs, and sustainability achievements. When this information is widely and transparently disseminated through various media channels—print, electronic, and digital—stakeholders have better access to assess the extent to which the company fulfills its social responsibilities. From the legitimacy theory perspective, these research findings are also highly relevant. Companies require support and acceptance from society to sustain their operations. Media exposure serves as a bridge between the company and society in delivering social responsibility messages. When the media positively and intensively covers a company's CSR activities, the company gains greater social legitimacy as it is viewed to meet societal norms, values, and expectations. Positive media exposure can also reduce perceptual gaps between the company and the public, thereby strengthening the perception that the company acts ethically, responsibly, and environmentally friendly.

These findings align with previous researches, such as studies by Puspita Sari (2022) and Sparta & Rheadanti (2019), which concluded that the media's role in communicating CSR information can influence how stakeholders perceive the company's value and integrity. High exposure to CSR activities also extends the social impact reach of the company, increases visibility, and enhances the company's reputation as an entity that positively contributes to social and environmental development. Empirically, the interaction analysis between CSR and media exposure variables shows a positive and significant interaction coefficient, indicating that when a company's CSR is supported by high media exposure, the influence of CSR on firm value becomes stronger compared to companies with low media exposure. In other words, media exposure acts as an amplifier that enlarges the impact of CSR on market perception and ultimately on the economic value of the company.

Conclusion

This study aims to examine the influence of CSR on firm value and analyze the role of media exposure as a moderating variable. Based on empirical analysis and theoretical review, several key conclusions are as follows:

1. CSR positively affects firm value: This finding supports stakeholder theory, explaining that companies actively fulfilling their social responsibilities gain support from stakeholders such as investors, consumers, employees, and the broader community. CSR increases stakeholders' trust and positive perceptions of the company, which subsequently influences an increase in firm value.

2. Media exposure strengthens the relationship between CSR and firm value: Media exposure serves as a strategic communication channel bridging CSR information to the public. From the legitimacy theory perspective, strong media exposure provides additional social legitimacy for the company and enhances public perception that the company acts responsibly. This results in greater firm value increases for companies with high media exposure levels.

3. Policy and regulatory implications highlight the importance of transparent and documented CSR reporting: This study aligns with the provisions of the Minister of Social Affairs Regulation No. 9 of 2020 concerning the Implementation of Corporate Social and Environmental Responsibility, and the Financial Services Authority Regulation No. 16/SEOJK.04/2021 mandating issuers and public companies to disclose CSR information transparently in annual reports. Therefore, CSR reporting and its media exposure become crucial aspects in shaping market perceptions of firm value.

Implications

This research can serve as an additional reference in the literature and as a basis for future studies related to CSR, firm value, and media exposure, as studies incorporating these variables are still relatively scarce. Based on stakeholder theory as proposed by Budianto & Suyono (2020), it is important to provide stakeholders with information regarding the company's social and environmental responsibilities, with the expectation that this will influence decision-making. The results indicate that CSR not only has a social impact but also exerts a direct economic effect on firm value due to the active involvement of stakeholders in evaluating a company's business practices. Effective CSR, when widely communicated through the media, enhances stakeholders' positive perceptions of the company. This study also supports the view that corporate legitimacy can be obtained or strengthened through CSR, especially when such practices receive adequate media exposure. This demonstrates that social legitimacy is determined not only by actions but also by the extent to which those actions are known and appreciated by the public.

References

- Abdullah, W., Syariati, A., & Hamid, R. (2017). Pengaruh corporate social responsibility (CSR), ukuran perusahaan dan interest based debt (IBD) terhadap nilai perusahaan pada perusahaan manufaktur di Jakarta. *Jurnal Manajemen Ide dan Inspirasi*, 4(2), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.24252/minds.v4i2.4192>
- Anisah, R. A. (2024). Kinerja lingkungan terhadap carbon emission disclosure dengan media exposure sebagai variabel moderasi pada manufaktur yang terdaftar di ISSI

- periode 2018–2022 [Unpublished manuscript]. [No further publication details provided].
- Apriyani, E. (2019). Pengaruh ukuran perusahaan terhadap zakat bank dengan profitabilitas sebagai pemoderasi. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Keuangan*, 3(1), 1–9.
- Ariani, D., Muthmainnah, M., & Ponto, S. (2024). Pengaruh pengungkapan corporate social responsibility, ukuran perusahaan, kepemilikan institusional dan kepemilikan manajerial terhadap nilai perusahaan. *Jurnal Bisnis Mahasiswa*, 4(2), 125–140. <https://doi.org/10.60036/jbm.v4i2.art2>
- Arifin, A. L., Vikaliana, R., Latunreng, W., & Bari, A. (2022). Identification and application of good corporate governance principles in the guarantee industry in Indonesia. *International Journal of Social Science and Business*, 6(3), 316–325. <https://doi.org/10.23887/ijssb.v6i1.44335>
- Bahriansyah, R. I., & Lestari Ginting, Y. (2022). Pengungkapan emisi karbon terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan media exposure sebagai variabel moderasi. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi & Perpajakan*, 9(2), 249–260. <https://doi.org/10.35838/jrap.2022.009.02.21>
- Budianto, R., & Suyono, E. (2020). Corporate social responsibility and factors affecting it: An empirical evidence from the Indonesian capital market. *International Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, 8(1), 239–253. <https://doi.org/10.35808/ijeba/422>
- Budiarti, M., & Raharjo, S. (2014). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) dari sudut pandang perusahaan. *Share: Jurnal Ekonomi dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 13–29. <https://doi.org/10.22373/share.v4i1.13045>
- Budimanta, A., Prasetijo, A., & Rudito, B. (2008). *Corporate social responsibility: Alternatif bagi pembangunan Indonesia*. ICSD.
- Dowling, J., & Pfeffer, J. (1975). Organizational legitimacy: Social values and organizational behavior. *Pacific Sociological Review*, 18(1), 122–136.
- Fitriana, A. (2024). *Buku ajar analisis laporan keuangan*. Akademi Keuangan & Perbankan Riau (AKBAR).
- Freeman, R. E., & McVea, J. (2005). A stakeholder approach to strategic management. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.263511>
- Ghaesani, N. S. (2017). Pengaruh pengungkapan corporate social responsibility, profitabilitas, ukuran perusahaan dan kinerja lingkungan terhadap nilai perusahaan [Unpublished manuscript].
- Ghozali, I. (2018). *Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 25*. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.

- Ghozali, I., & Chariri, A. (2007). *Accounting theory*. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hermawan, S., Hanun, N., Nirwana, N. Q., & Candrawati, C. (2021). Intellectual capital, market value, and financial performance: Indonesia and Malaysia's banking companies. *Journal of Accounting and Strategic Finance*, 4(2), 135–151. <https://doi.org/10.33005/jasf.v4i2.142>
- Julekhah, F., & Rahmawati, E. (2019). Pengaruh media exposure, sensitivitas industri, kepemilikan asing, kepemilikan publik dan profitabilitas terhadap environmental disclosure dan dampaknya terhadap nilai perusahaan. *Reviu Akuntansi dan Bisnis Indonesia*, 3(1), 50–66. <https://doi.org/10.18196/rab.030136>
- Karundeng, F., Nangoi, G. B., & Karamoy, H. (2017). Analisis pengaruh corporate social responsibility terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan profitabilitas, kepemilikan manajemen dan ukuran perusahaan sebagai variabel moderasi (Studi empiris pada perusahaan pertambangan yang terdaftar di Bursa Efek Jakarta). *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi dan Auditing "Goodwill,"* 8(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.35800/jjs.v8i2.16901>
- Khofifah, D. N., Meiriasari, V., & Pebriani, R. A. (2024). Pengaruh corporate social responsibility, ukuran perusahaan, dan profitabilitas terhadap nilai perusahaan. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis dan Kewirausahaan*, 8(3), 645–656. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jmbk.v8i3.30225>
- Kivits, R., & Sawang, S. (2021). Stakeholder theory. In *Contributions to management science* (pp. 1–8). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-70428-5_1
- Lo, E. W. (2012). Pengaruh tingkat kesulitan keuangan terhadap manajemen laba: Teori keagenan versus teori signaling. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi dan Keuangan*, 8(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.21460/jrak.2012.81.27>
- Madan, D. B., & Wang, K. (2024). Financial finance. *International Journal of Theoretical and Applied Finance*, 27(3), Article 2450011. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219024924500110>
- Mardikanto, T. (2014). *CSR (Corporate social responsibility) (Tanggungjawab sosial korporasi)*. Alfabeta.
- Murnita, P. E. M., & Putra, I. M. P. D. (2018). Pengaruh corporate social responsibility terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan profitabilitas dan leverage sebagai variabel pemoderasi. *E-Jurnal Akuntansi*, 23(2), 1470–1496. <https://doi.org/10.24843/EJA.2018.v23.i02.p25>
- Ningrum, E. P. (2022). Nilai perusahaan (Konsep dan aplikasi). *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 3(1), 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.263510>
- Nurhayati, R. (2011). Social responsibility journal. *The Electronic Library*, 34(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.265511>

- Octoriawan, A., & Rusliati, E. (2019). Corporate social responsibility, kepemilikan manajerial terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan moderasi ukuran perusahaan. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Kontemporer*, 11(2), 60–68. <https://doi.org/10.23969/jrak.v11i2.2771>
- Omar, S., Al, P., & Ghassan, T. (2017). The impact of economic development on enhancing the integrity of import and anti-corruption system. *International Journal of Business and Statistical Analysis*, 8(11), 146–152. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.263521>
- Panggabean, M. R. (2018). Pengaruh corporate social responsibility, ukuran perusahaan, struktur modal dan tax avoidance terhadap nilai perusahaan. *Kajian Bisnis STIE Widya Wiwaha*, 26(1), 82–94. <https://doi.org/10.32477/jkb.v26i1.266>
- Praditya, A., & Utomo, D. C. (2022). Systematic literature review: Hubungan sistem informasi akuntansi dengan kinerja perusahaan. *Diponegoro Journal of Accounting*, 11(4), 1–13.
- Prasetyo, A. (2019). Pengaruh corporate social responsibility terhadap citra perusahaan pada masa pandemi Covid-19 (Studi empiris pada perusahaan PT. Asia Menara Perkasa, Lampung). *Jurkami: Jurnal Ilmiah Bidang Sosial, Ekonomi, Budaya, Teknologi dan Pendidikan*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.263111>
- Puspita Sari, S. (2022). Pengaruh pengungkapan lingkungan dan media exposure terhadap nilai perusahaan (Studi empiris pada perusahaan makanan dan minuman yang terdaftar di BEI). *Jurnal Akuntansi Aisyah*, 4(2), 24–29. <https://doi.org/10.57084/jata.v4i2.24>
- Rawi, & Muchlish, M. (2010). Kepemilikan manajemen, kepemilikan institusi, leverage dan corporate social responsibility. *Simposium Jurnal Akuntansi*, 1–28.
- Reverte, C. (2008). Determinants of corporate social responsibility disclosure ratings by Spanish listed firms. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 88(2), 351–366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-008-9968-9>
- Sari, M. S. (2021). Pengaruh pengungkapan corporate social responsibility (CSR) terhadap nilai perusahaan (Studi kasus pada subsektor tekstil dan garmen yang terdaftar di Bursa Efek Indonesia (BEI) tahun 2017–2019). *Journal of Accounting, Taxing and Auditing*, 2(2), 2019–2022. <https://doi.org/10.57084/jata.v2i2.690>
- Sartono, A. (2012). *Manajemen keuangan teori dan aplikasi*. BPFY Yogyakarta.
- Sayekti, Y., & Wondabio, L. (2007). Pengaruh CSR disclosure terhadap earning response coefficient. *Simposium Nasional Akuntansi X*, 1–24.
- Setiawan, K., Novitasari, N. L. G., & Widhiastuti, N. L. P. (2021). Pengaruh ukuran perusahaan terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan corporate social responsibility sebagai variabel pemoderasi. *Jurnal Kharisma*, 3(1), 302–312. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.163511>

- Sparta, S., & Rheadanti, D. K. (2019). Pengaruh media exposure terhadap pengungkapan corporate social responsibility perusahaan manufaktur terdaftar di BEI. *Equity*, 22(1), 12–25. <https://doi.org/10.34209/equ.v22i1.903>
- Spence, M. (1973). Job market signaling. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 87(3), 355–374. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1882010>
- Sujarweni, V. W. (2019). *Metodologi penelitian bisnis dan ekonomi*. Pustaka Baru Press.
- Tino, I. W. R., & Sudana, I. P. (2025). Peran corporate social responsibility memediasi pengaruh penerapan green accounting dan kinerja lingkungan terhadap profitabilitas perusahaan yang terdaftar di BEI. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 10(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.263211>
- Titi, S., Sabar, W., & Sixpria, N. (2011). Pengaruh pengungkapan tanggung jawab sosial dan praktik tata kelola perusahaan terhadap nilai perusahaan. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 10(2), 95–105.
- Uniarnews. (2024, July 24). Korupsi tambang timah: Kerugian lingkungan mencapai Rp 271 triliun. *Universitas Airlangga News*. <https://unair.ac.id/korupsi-tambang-timah-kerugian-lingkungan-mencapai-rp-271-triliun/>
- Widianingsih, D. (2018). Kepemilikan manajerial, kepemilikan institusional, komisaris independen, serta komite audit pada nilai perusahaan dengan pengungkapan CSR sebagai variabel moderating dan firm size sebagai variabel kontrol. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Pajak*, 19(1), 38–50. <https://doi.org/10.29040/jap.v19i1.196>
- Wongso, A. (2012). Pengaruh kebijakan dividen, struktur kepemilikan, dan kebijakan hutang terhadap nilai perusahaan dalam perspektif teori agensi dan teori signaling. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Manajemen*, 1(5), 1–6.
- Wulandari, N. M. I., & Wiksuana, I. G. B. (2017). Peranan corporate social responsibility dalam memoderasi pengaruh profitabilitas, leverage dan ukuran perusahaan terhadap nilai perusahaan. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 6(3), 1278–1311.

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